

Spectrophotometric Determination of Chromium in Steel by Extraction of its Ion Association Complex with Tetraphenylarsonium Chloride**

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Chromium(VI) forms ion association complex with tetraphenylarsonium chloride extractable into chloroform and 1,2-dichloroethane. Based on the ultraviolet absorption of this ion pair in 1,2-dichloroethane, the better extractant of the two, a method for the determination of chromium was evolved. Interfering effect of a number of ions were investigated. The relative ease of conversion of chromium(III) to chromium(VI) affords a means of its separation from most of the commonly associated elements. Methods have also been developed to remove the interference due to a few anions that are extractable with tetraphenylarsonium chloride into 1,2-dichloroethane. The method was subsequently used in the determination of chromium in standard steel samples.

SEVERAL reagents are known which are used for the determination of small amounts of chromium by the spectrophotometric method. The most sensitive reaction for determining chromium is the one between S-diphenyl carbazide and chromium(VI) in acid solution¹. The resulting red-violet species is reported to be extractable by organic solvents like isoamyl alcohol², chloroform³ and cyclohexanol⁴ and was used in recent years for spectrophotometric determination of chromium(VI)⁵⁻⁷ using prior separation methods. Other reagents used for the determination of chromium are NH₄-pyrrolidine-1-carbodithioate⁸, uramildiacetic acid⁹, 3-hydroxy-4-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylazo)naphthalene-1-sulphonic acid¹⁰ and mercaptacetic acid¹¹. Majumder and De¹², however, used 2-thenoyltrifluoroacetone (TTA) for direct spectrophotometric determination of chromium by extracting the Cr(III)-TTA complex into benzene.

It has been found, following the suggestion of Alimarin Perezhogin¹³ that chromium(VI) forms ion association complex with tetraphenylarsonium cation extractable into chloroform or 1,2-dichloroethane, a fact which had been reported earlier by Hala *et al*¹⁴. Baishya and Heslop¹⁵ determined chromium in aluminium alloys both by neutron activation and isotope dilution analysis based on the principle of stoichiometric extraction with tetraphenylarsonium chloride.

In the present work spectrophotometric determination of chromium by extraction of its ion pair with tetraphenylarsonium chloride into 1,2-dichloroethane was investigated. The relative ease of inter conversion of chromium(III) to chromium(VI) and formation of easily extractable Cr(VI)-TPA ion pair made it possible to determine chromium in presence of most of the commonly associated elements. The method was applied in the

determination of chromium in standard steel samples.

Experimental

Apparatus: Absorbance measurements were made with a Beckman DK-2 spectrophotometer.

Reagent: A 0.01 M solution of tetraphenylarsonium chloride (Fluka A.G., Buchs S.G.) in distilled water was employed as the reagent.

Standard solution: 0.3734 g of potassium chromate (AnalaR) was dissolved in 1 N H₂SO₄ in a 100 ml standard flask and the volume was made up with the same acid. The resulting solution contained 0.0001 g of chromium per ml and was used as a stock solution. Solutions of lower concentrations were prepared from the stock solution by dilution with 1 N H₂SO₄.

Other compounds used for studying interferences were ferric ammonium sulphate, cadmium sulphate, copper sulphate, mercuric chloride, ammonium molybdate, sodium tungstate, potassium permanganate, potassium thiocyanate, ammonium fluoride, sodium oxalate, sodium vanadate, sodium perchlorate and potassium antimonyl tartrate.

Procedure for calibration: An aliquot of the standard solution containing 50 µg to 200 µg of chromium was taken in several different separating funnels. The volume in each was made 5 ml by adding 1 N H₂SO₄. To each of these solutions was then added 1 ml of 0.01 M tetraphenylarsonium chloride reagent. The resulting mixture was then shaken for 2 min with 5 ml of 1,2-dichloroethane. The organic layer was separated and the absorbance was measured at 363 nm against the pure solvent. A plot of these absorbance values against concentration gave a straight line indicating that Beer's law

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is obeyed over the concentration range 10 to 40 μg of chromium per ml of the organic phase.

The process was repeated in a few more aliquots taken at random and the amount of chromium calculated from the calibration curve showed good recovery of chromium with an error within 2 per cent.

Experiment on the study of interferences : In a separate set of experiments, an aliquot of the standard solution containing 100 μg of chromium was taken in each of the several different separating funnels. To each of these, an aqueous solution of metal ions viz., Fe^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Sb^{3+} and the anions MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} , MnO_4^- , CNS^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, F^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, VO_3^- and ClO_4^- in amounts equal to and three and five times the amount of chromium was added. The volume in each was made 5 ml by adding 1 N H_2SO_4 . To each of these solutions was then added 1 ml of the tetraphenylarsonium chloride reagent. The resulting mixture was extracted as above with 5 ml of 1,2-dichloroethane and the absorbance of the organic phase was measured at 363 nm. Another aliquot containing 100 μg of chromium in absence of other ions was treated in a similar manner and the absorbance of the organic extract was measured at 363 nm.

Removal of interference due to :

(a) *Oxalate :* An aliquot containing 100 μg of chromium was taken in two different separating funnels. To each of these solutions, a solution containing 100 μg and 500 μg of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ was added separately. The resulting solutions were warmed and a dilute solution of equivalent amount of KMnO_4 was added dropwise. The solutions were then treated with 2 ml of 10% ceric sulphate solution and were boiled for 10 min. The resulting solutions were made 1 N in H_2SO_4 and was extracted into isobutyl methyl ketone taking 5 ml of the solvent. Chromium in the organic phase was then back extracted to water and the aqueous layer was made 1 N with respect to H_2SO_4 to which 1 ml of tetraphenylarsonium chloride reagent was added. Extractions and absorbance measurements were made as described above. The amount of chromium calculated showed cent per cent recovery of chromium in both.

(b) *Permanganate :* An aliquot of the standard solution containing 100 μg of chromium was taken in two different separating funnels. To each of these, solutions containing 100 μg and 500 μg of MnO_4^- was added separately. Each of these solutions was warmed with 2 to 3 drops of absolute alcohol. The resulting colourless solutions were then treated with 2 ml of 10% ceric sulphate solution. Chromium as chromate was then separated, extracted and absorbance of the extract was measured in a similar manner as described above. A good recovery of chromium was obtained in both the cases.

Determination of chromium in high speed steel and alloy steel : 0.1 g of high speed steel (No. 64b) and 0.6 g of alloy steel (No. 60b), procured from

the Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., was weighed out accurately in two different beakers. The alloys were then dissolved in the minimum volume of concentrated nitric acid by heating. To each of the solutions, after cooling, was added 2 ml of 50% H_2SO_4 . The resulting mixture was heated till the evolution of white fumes. Solutions were then diluted and boiled with 2 ml of 10% ceric sulphate solution for about 10 min. Solutions were cooled and made 1 N in H_2SO_4 and were extracted with 10 ml of isobutyl methyl ketone for 3 min. Organic extracts were washed with 1 N H_2SO_4 and the dichromate was back extracted by shaking the organic layer repeatedly with distilled water. Combined aqueous layers were transferred into two separate 100 ml standard flasks and the required amount of 50% H_2SO_4 was added to make these 1 N in H_2SO_4 in the made up solution.

Separate aliquots from each solution were taken in different separating funnels, to each of which 1 ml of 0.01 M tetraphenylarsonium chloride reagent was added. Volume of the resulting solution was made 5 ml with 1 N H_2SO_4 and was then extracted with 5 ml of 1,2-dichloroethane. Absorbance in the organic layer was measured at 363 nm and the amount of chromium was calculated from the calibration curve. The average of a number of determinations from different weighed samples are shown below :

Samples	Chromium found	Chromium present
High speed steel (No. 64b)	4.4%	4.55%
Alloy steel (No. 60b)	0.72%	0.75%

Discussion

Chromium(VI) forms ion pair with tetraphenylarsonium chloride and the resulting ion association compound, which is precipitated in aqueous solution, 1 N in sulphuric acid was found to be extractable into chloroform and 1,2-dichloroethane. Of the two solvents, 1,2-dichloroethane proved to be a better extractant for the ion pair which absorbed in the ultraviolet region having maximum absorption at 363 nm (Fig. 1). Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 10 to 40 μg of chromium per ml of the organic phase.

An examination of the interfering effect of a number of metal ions viz., Fe^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Sb^{3+} in varying amounts revealed that except Sb^{3+} , none of these ions interfered. The organic extract of Cr(VI)-TPA complex was found to be colourless in presence of Sb^{3+} probably due to the reduction of Cr(VI) by Sb^{3+} . Other metal ions did not interfere as there was no possibility of formation of their halo complexes capable of forming ion pair with tetraphenylarsonium chloride. Similar examination with anions, having possibility of ion pair formation with the reagent, viz., MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} , MnO_4^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, CNS^- , F^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, VO_3^- and ClO_4^- were made. Of these

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (A) tetraphenylarsonium chromate in 1,2-dichloroethane containing 20 μg of chromium per ml against solvent (B) the reagent blank against solvent.

only MnO_4^- and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ interfered even when present in amounts equal to chromium. Oxalate interfered only slightly. Thiocyanate, though did not interfere in equal amounts, interfered when present in five time excess. However, the relative ease of interconversion of Cr(III) to Cr(VI) made it possible to separate chromium from most of the commonly associated interfering elements.

Interference due to $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ ion was removed by KMnO_4 oxidation. Chromium was then separated from any excess permanganate by extraction with isobutyl methyl ketone from 1 N sulphuric acid and

it was determined subsequently by back extracting to water. Interference due to MnO_4^- ion was removed by reduction with alcohol when both MnO_4^- and CrO_4^{2-} were reduced. Chromium was later oxidised with ceric sulphate in acid solution, separated and estimated with good recovery of chromium.

The method was used for estimation of chromium in high speed steel and alloy steel and the amount of chromium found was in good agreement with the standard value with an error within 3 to 4 per cent.

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